

Locally resonant metamaterials utilizing Dynamic Directional Amplification: an application for seismic mitigation

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Abstract: Locally resonant metamaterials (LRMs), with unit-cells exhibiting local resonance, present unique wave propagation properties as a result of their spatial periodicity. However, these structures present certain limitations in designing systems with wide bandgaps in the low-frequency range. Aiming to confront the main practical challenges encountered in such cases, including heavy parasitic oscillating masses, a simple dynamic directional amplification (DDA) mechanism is proposed. This amplifier is designed to comprise the same mass and use the same damping element of a reference two-dimensional (2D) mass-in-mass metamaterial. Thus, no increase in the structure's mass or viscous damping is required. The proposed DDA can be realized by imposing kinematic constraints to the structure's degrees of freedom (DoFs), hence increasing inertia to the desired direction of motion. A discrete element lattice model based on mass, stiffness, and damping elements, is used to establish dispersion behavior and frequency response. The numerical results of an indicative case study indicate significant improvements and advantages over the reference LRM, such as broader bandgaps and increased damping ratio. Finally, a conceptual design of a metabarrier based on this concept

indicates the usage of this mechanism in potential applications, such as seismic wave mitigation and protection of structures.

Keywords: metamaterials, local resonance, seismic isolation, bandgaps, dynamic directional amplifier

1. Introduction

The propagation of various types of waves (such as acoustic, elastic, and electromagnetic waves) within artificially engineered periodic structures, namely phononic or acoustic metamaterials, has recently drawn the interest of a large number of researchers and engineering scientists [1]. Specifically, acoustic metamaterials (AMs) exhibit extraordinary dynamic properties due to their local features and uniquely engineered configurations, namely their "microstructures". These microstructures are usually materialized in the form of locally resonant periodic elements or other dissipation mechanisms incorporated within a host structure. The material parameters of metamaterials can be tuned to any values in material space by adjusting their microstructures. In other words, their architecture can be designed to produce the desired response, including negative effective mass [2–5], negative Poisson's ratio [6], and negative stiffness [7]. For example, locally resonant phononic crystals can exhibit negative mass density [8] at the frequencies where sub-wavelength microstructures resonate and move out of phase with the excitation.

One of the most appealing properties of such structures is their filtering effect and the consequent formation of bandgaps. This implies that when the frequency of an impacting excitation falls into the generated blind zone, the propagation of waves is blocked, thus forming a bandgap. Locally resonant bandgaps correspond to internal resonances of the periodic microstructures and can be generated using resonators [9–14].

A new branch of LRMs has emerged recently, namely the seismic metamaterials, proposed as a solution to mitigate low-frequency seismic excitation and hence, protect structures from the detrimental effect of earthquakes [15–20]. This LRM category includes periodic and locally resonant large-scale features (e.g., foundations, metabarriers, etc.) that attenuate seismic wave propagation at a sub-wavelength scale. Resonant metafoundations consist of a chain of resonant mass-stiffness-damping systems (such as an array of concrete plates) embedded below the foundations to isolate the superstructure from seismic body waves [21–23]. On the other hand, metabarriers comprise a lattice of locally resonant mass-in-mass structures, embedded close to the soil surface, capable of protecting the surrounding buildings and infrastructure from surface waves [18,24–26].

Nonetheless, conventional locally resonant metamaterials (LRMs) [2] may require hefty internal parasitic masses, as well as additional constraints at the amplitudes of the internally oscillating locally resonating structures, which may prohibit their practical implementation [27]. Therefore, achieving wide and low-frequency bandgaps, based solely on traditional LRM structures is a challenge. Recently, attempts have been made towards artificially increasing the resonating mass's inertia via negative stiffness elements or amplification mechanisms. For example, the inclusion of negative stiffness elements to the oscillating system shows promising results in addressing this issue, to a certain extent, revealing the

potential of the KDamper (KD) concept [19,28,29] towards the design of low-frequency acoustic metamaterials [30–32]. Similarly, inspired by the successful application of inertial amplifiers in engineering applications, several works proved their suitability in the context of periodic structures [33–37]. Researchers [27,38,39] studied the longitudinal elastic wave propagation characteristics of inertant acoustic metamaterial configurations having inerters either in the local attachments or in the lattice, using effective models for their one-dimensional discrete element lattice chains. These analyses indicated that up or downshifting of the bandgap frequency range and its extent depends on the inerter configuration while retaining static mass addition to the host structure to a minimum level. Frandsen [40] investigated wave motion propagation in a continuous elastic rod with periodically attached inertial amplification mechanisms, which he utilized in a manner that alters the intrinsic properties of the continuous structure. He concluded that the inertial amplification system is superior, as the simple local resonance system requires approximately twenty times heavier mass to obtain a comparable bandgap width. Li and Li [41] extended Frandsen's model and included inertial amplification to infinite elastic beams.

In this paper, a simple dynamic directional amplifier (DDA) [42] is introduced as a means to increase the resonating mass of an LRM structure artificially. The DDA mechanism is realized without additional masses or complex geometries since the amplification can be achieved by coupling the kinematic DoFs of the resonating mass with a rigid link improving inertia and damping [43] on the desired direction of motion. The main aim of this study is to illustrate, via the use of a formal mathematical framework, that we can enhance the performance of LR structures while retaining or even improving the practical constraints such as having compact, lightweight, and buildable unit-cells. Towards this goal, a mass-in-mass model is adopted, and a preliminary parametric analysis is performed using both Bloch's theory [44] on two-dimensional infinite lattices and conventional vibration theory on finite lattices. A numerical example is studied as a seismic mitigation application in order to highlight the advantages of the proposed arrangement over the initial study. To this end, a conceptual design of a seismic metamaterial in the form of a metabarrier is proposed and an investigation of its response under seismic excitation is analyzed. Results indicate the beneficial role of the device and DDA mechanism, hence placing the concept as a compelling alternative to existing seismic protection technologies

2. Mathematical modeling

2.1. Overview of the Dynamic Directional Amplification (DDA) Mechanism

The basic layout of the amplifier, namely the DDA mechanism, is depicted in Fig. 1. Connecting the amplification mass to the origin of the local coordinate system (CSYS) via a hinged, rigid rod, which is assumed to be massless for the purpose of this analysis, imposes a kinematic constraint between the DoFs u and v . The lumped parameter model is described by the coordinates of the amplification mass (m) at a generic position $A(x, y) = (x_0 + u, y_0 - v)$, where x_0, y_0 are the initial coordinates of the mass. The initial angle

between the vertical axis and the link is denoted by $\varphi = \text{atan}\left(\frac{x_0}{y_0}\right)$, while θ denotes the rotation of the rod at the generic position A of the moving mass. As a result, the kinematics of the system cause amplification to the mass m . Via the application of Lagrange's principle and after linearization (see Appendix A), the mechanisms governing the equation of motion are expressed as follows:

$$m[1 + \tan^2(\varphi)]\ddot{u} + [k_x + k_y \tan^2(\varphi)]u = F \quad (1)$$

Where k_x and k_y are the springs stiffness on the horizontal and vertical directions. By setting $\rho = \tan\varphi$, the coupling of u, v DoFs can be simplified as

$$m[1 + \rho^2]\ddot{u} + [k_x + k_y \rho^2]u = F \quad (2)$$

It should be noted that Eq. (2) holds only for small displacements of the mass m as the springs' deformations are nonlinear functions of u, v (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamic directional amplification (DDA) mechanism, where the motion v of mass m is kinematically constrained to the motion u , (a) initial mass position (b) mass position at deformed state.

2.2. Dispersion analysis of Locally resonant metamaterials (LRMs)

Fig. 2 illustrates the primary unit-cell of a simple mass-in-mass configuration, which consists of an external mass (m_L), an internal resonator (m_R), and the corresponding massless springs and dashpots. Based on this simple configuration, the enhanced unit-cells are conceptualized. Fig. 2a depicts the configuration of a traditional locally resonant unit-cell and Fig. 2b illustrates the configuration with the DDA attached in the resonating mass (m_R).

Fig. 2. The periodic mass-in-mass unit-cell (a) w/o DDA (b) with DDA attached in the resonating mass (m_R).

By placing such units in a lattice, at a distance $L=\alpha_x=\alpha_y$, an infinitely periodic material is composed, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Harmonic wave propagation in the mass-in-mass lattice system is considered.

Fig. 3. 2-D spring-mass effective lattice.

The set of equations that describe the harmonic motion of the simple typical unit-cell of Fig. 2a, at location p, q , can be expressed as [43]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m_L \ddot{u}_L^{p,q} + k_{Lx} (2u_L^{p,q} - u_L^{p-1,q} - u_L^{p+1,q}) + k_{Rx} (u_L^{p,q} - u_R^{p,q}) \\
 + c_{Lx} (2\dot{u}_L^{p,q} - \dot{u}_L^{p-1,q} - \dot{u}_L^{p+1,q}) + c_{Rx} (\dot{u}_L^{p,q} - \dot{u}_R^{p,q}) = 0
 \end{aligned} \quad (3a)$$

$$m_R \ddot{u}_R^{p,q} + k_{Rx} (u_R^{p,q} - u_L^{p,q}) + c_{Rx} (\dot{u}_R^{p,q} - \dot{u}_L^{p,q}) = 0 \quad (3b)$$

$$m_L \ddot{v}_L^{p,q} + k_{Ly} (2v_L^{p,q} - v_L^{p,q-1} - v_L^{p,q+1}) + k_{Ry} (v_L^{p,q} - v_R^{p,q}) + c_{Ly} (2\dot{v}_L^{p,q} - \dot{v}_L^{p,q-1} - \dot{v}_L^{p,q+1}) + c_{Ry} (\dot{v}_L^{p,q} - \dot{v}_R^{p,q}) = 0 \quad (3c)$$

$$m_R \ddot{v}_R^{p,q} + k_{Ry} (v_R^{p,q} - v_L^{p,q}) + c_{Ry} (\dot{v}_R^{p,q} - \dot{v}_L^{p,q}) = 0 \quad (3d)$$

The displacement of a DoF at a specific position of the lattice may be expressed in a complex notation as:

$$u_{p,q} = \widehat{U}_{p,q} e^{\lambda t} = \widetilde{U} e^{i(p\kappa_x \alpha_x + q\kappa_y \alpha_y)} = \widetilde{U} e^{i(p\mu_x + q\mu_y)} \quad (4)$$

where \widetilde{U} is the wave amplitude, κ_x, κ_y the wavenumbers and μ_x, μ_y the propagation constants along the horizontal and vertical directions.

In the time part of the solution, the parameter λ_s is defined as $\lambda_s = \pm j\omega_s(\kappa)$, or in the case where the attenuation between the unit-cells is considered $\lambda_s = -\zeta_s(\kappa)\omega_s(\kappa) \pm j\omega_{d_s}(\kappa)$, where s represents the branch number, $\zeta_s(\kappa)$ is the wavenumber-dependent damping ratio and $\omega_s(\kappa)$ is the wavenumber-dependent frequency (dispersion relation). As a result, the imaginary part is the frequency of the damped wave propagation, $\omega_{d_s}(\kappa) = \text{Im}[\lambda_s(\kappa)]$, and the damping ratio is calculated as:

$$\zeta_s(k) = -\frac{\text{Re}[\lambda_s(\kappa)]}{|\lambda_s(\kappa)|} \quad (5)$$

Utilizing Bloch's theorem, the spatial part of the solution is expressed as:

$$u_L^{p,q} = \widetilde{U}_L^{p,q} e^{i\kappa_x p \alpha_x + i\kappa_y q \alpha_y} e^{\lambda t} = \widetilde{U}_L^{p,q} e^{ip\mu_x + iq\mu_y} e^{\lambda t} \quad (6a)$$

$$u_L^{p+1,q} = \widetilde{U}_L^{p,q} e^{i\kappa_x(p+1)\alpha_x + i\kappa_y q \alpha_y} e^{\lambda t} = \widetilde{U}_L^{p,q} e^{i(p+1)\mu_x + iq\mu_y} e^{\lambda t} = u_L^{p,q} e^{i\mu_x} \quad (6b)$$

$$u_L^{p-1,q} = \widetilde{U}_L^{p,q} e^{i\kappa_x(p-1)\alpha_x + i\kappa_y q \alpha_y} e^{\lambda t} = \widetilde{U}_L^{p,q} e^{i(p-1)\mu_x + iq\mu_y} e^{\lambda t} = u_L^{p,q} e^{-i\mu_x} \quad (6c)$$

$$v_L^{p,q} = V_L^{p,q} e^{i\kappa_x p \alpha_x + i\kappa_y q \alpha_y} e^{\lambda t} = V_L^{p,q} e^{ip\mu_x + iq\mu_y} e^{\lambda t} \quad (6d)$$

$$v_L^{p,q+1} = \widetilde{V}_L^{p,q} e^{i\kappa_x p \alpha_x + i\kappa_y(q+1)\alpha_y} e^{\lambda t} = \widetilde{V}_L^{p,q} e^{ip\mu_x + i(q+1)\mu_y} e^{\lambda t} = v_L^{p,q} e^{i\mu_y} \quad (6e)$$

$$v_L^{p,q-1} = \widetilde{V}_L^{p,q} e^{i\kappa_x p \alpha_x + i\kappa_y(q-1)\alpha_y} e^{\lambda t} = \widetilde{V}_L^{p,q} e^{ip\mu_x + i(q-1)\mu_y} e^{\lambda t} = v_L^{p,q} e^{-i\mu_y} \quad (6f)$$

Substituting these relations into the equations of motion and incorporating the conditions for unit-cell periodicity yields four homogeneous equations, which can be written in a matrix notation as follows:

$$[-\lambda^2 \mathbf{M}_{LRM} + \lambda \mathbf{C}_{LRM} + \mathbf{K}_{LRM}] \mathbf{u}_{LRM} = 0 \quad (7)$$

where

$$\mathbf{M}_{LRM} = \begin{bmatrix} m_L & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_L & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_R & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m_R \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{LRM} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{Lx}(2 - (e^{-i\mu_x} + e^{i\mu_x}) + c_{Rx}) & 0 & -c_{Rx} & 0 \\ 0 & c_{Ly}(2 - (e^{-i\mu_y} + e^{i\mu_y}) + c_{Ry}) & 0 & -c_{Ry} \\ -c_{Ry} & 0 & c_{Rx} & 0 \\ 0 & -c_{Rx} & 0 & c_{Ry} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8b)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{LRM} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{Lx}(2 - (e^{-i\mu_x} + e^{i\mu_x}) + k_{Rx}) & 0 & -k_{Rx} & 0 \\ 0 & k_{Ly}(2 - (e^{-i\mu_y} + e^{i\mu_y}) + k_{Ry}) & 0 & -k_{Ry} \\ -k_{Rx} & 0 & k_{Rx} & 0 \\ 0 & -k_{Ry} & 0 & k_{Ry} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8c)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{LRM} = \begin{bmatrix} u_L^{p,q} \\ v_L^{p,q} \\ u_R^{p,q} \\ v_R^{p,q} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8d)$$

Assuming for simplicity reasons that $k_{Lx}=k_{Ly}=k_L$ and $k_{Rx}=k_{Ry}=k_R$, and that the system is undamped allows the investigation of the problem by adopting the one-dimensional propagation theory.

Utilization of the trigonometric transformation $\beta=2-(e^{i\mu}+e^{-i\mu})=2(1-\cos\mu)$ leads to the following dispersion equation [1]:

$$m_L m_R \omega^4 - [(m_L + m_R)k_R + 2m_R k_L(1 - \cos\mu)]\omega^2 + 2k_L k_R(1 - \cos\mu) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Based on [24], we can deduce a rough estimate of the required quantities to obtain a bandgap within the frequency region of our preference, as follows:

$$m_R = \left[\left(\frac{f_H}{f_L} \right)^2 - 1 \right] m_L \quad (10)$$

$$k_R = 4\pi^2 f_L^2 m_R = 4\pi^2 (f_H^2 - f_L^2) m_L \quad (11)$$

with f_L and f_H (Hz) denoting the low and high threshold of the selected bandgap, respectively.

Once the equation of motion of the simple LRM is derived, we can study the band structure of the LRM-DDA metamaterial. The DoFs of the coupled system are the following:

$$\mathbf{u}_{LRM-DDA} = \mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{u}_{LRM} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \rho \end{bmatrix}^T \mathbf{u}_{LRM} \quad (12)$$

The system with the amplified masses m_R can be calculated by multiplying \mathbf{M}_{LRM} , \mathbf{C}_{LRM} and \mathbf{K}_{LRM} by the transformation matrix \mathbf{Q} . The dispersion relationship of the LRM structure with Dynamic Directional Amplifiers is given by:

$$\det[-\lambda^2 \mathbf{M}_{LRM-DDA} + \lambda \mathbf{C}_{LRM-DDA} + \mathbf{K}_{LRM-DDA}] = 0 \quad (13)$$

where

$$\mathbf{M}_{LRM-DDA} = \mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{M}_{LRM} \mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} m_L & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_R(1+\rho^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14a)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{C}_{LRM} \mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 2c_{Lx}(1 - \cos\mu_x) + c_{Rx} & 0 & -k_{Rx} \\ 0 & 2c_{Ly}(1 - \cos\mu_y) + c_{Ry} & -\rho c_{Ry} \\ -c_{Rx} & -\rho c_{Ry} & c_{Rx} + \rho^2 c_{Ry} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14b)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{LRM-DDA} = \mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{K}_{LRM} \mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 2k_{Lx}(1 - \cos\mu_x) + k_{Rx} & 0 & -k_{Rx} \\ 0 & 2k_{Ly}(1 - \cos\mu_y) + k_{Ry} & -\rho k_{Ry} \\ -k_{Rx} & -\rho k_{Ry} & k_{Rx} + \rho^2 k_{Ry} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14c)$$

2.3. Structural dynamics of the finite lattice

Fig. 4 presents a lattice configuration with finite number of locally resonant unit-cells. Consequently, the equation of motion of the metamaterial, for $N_x \times N_y$ number of unit-cells is expressed in matrix formulation as:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{F}e^{\lambda t} \quad (15)$$

where $[\mathbf{M}_{n \times n}]$, $[\mathbf{C}_{n \times n}]$, $[\mathbf{K}_{n \times n}]$, $[\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{n \times 1}]$, $[\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{n \times 1}]$, $[\mathbf{u}_{n \times 1}]$, $[\mathbf{F}_{n \times 1}]$ and n is the number of degrees of freedom (DoFs) of the metamaterial.

Fig. 4. Structure with $N_x \times N_y$ unit-cells with a periodic loading acting at the right boundary.

For the case of the lattice without the amplification mechanism, $n = 4N_x N_y$. On the other hand, for the lattice with the *DDA*, $n = 3N_x N_y$, and the global mass $[\mathbf{M}_{LRM-DDA}^G]$, damping $[\mathbf{C}_{LRM-DDA}^G]$ and stiffness $[\mathbf{K}_{LRM-DDA}^G]$ matrices can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}_{LRM-DDA}^G = \mathbf{Q}_G^T \mathbf{M}_{LRM}^G \mathbf{Q}_G \quad (16a)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{LRM-DDA}^G = \mathbf{Q}_G^T \mathbf{C}_{LRM}^G \mathbf{Q}_G \quad (16b)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{LRM-DDA}^G = \mathbf{Q}_G^T \mathbf{K}_{LRM}^G \mathbf{Q}_G \quad (16c)$$

The transform matrix is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{Q}_G^{(4N_x N_y) \times (3N_x N_y)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & & \dots & & & & & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & & & & & & \\ & 0 & 1 & & & & & & \\ & 0 & \rho & 0 & & & & & \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 & & & & \vdots \\ & & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & & & \\ & & & 0 & \rho & 1 & 0 & & \\ & & & & 0 & 0 & 1 & & \\ 0 & & & \dots & & 0 & \rho & & \end{bmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

The stiffness $[\mathbf{K}^G]$, damping $[\mathbf{C}^G]$ and mass $[\mathbf{M}^G]$ matrices of each unit-cell are assembled as in any finite element analysis to produce the Global matrices of the periodic structure. Assuming that the finite lattice is excited harmonically at the input nodes with frequency ω , the force magnitude vector \mathbf{F} is equal to zero everywhere except from the row or column corresponding to the component of the input node, for which it has unit amplitude. The transfer matrix of each degree of freedom may be calculated by the following expression:

$$\mathbf{T}\mathbf{F} = [-\lambda^2 \mathbf{M} + \lambda \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{K}]^{-1} \mathbf{F}, \quad (18)$$

Thus, the frequency response of the nodal displacements can be obtained. In this case, u_{in} denotes the displacement of the outer masses (m_L), where the input excitation is applied, and u_{fin} denotes the displacement of the rear outer mass of the last unit-cells.

The Frequency Response Function (**FRF**) of the metamaterial is consequently expressed in decibels as follows:

$$FRF = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{u_{fin}}{u_{in}} \right) \quad (19)$$

3. Numerical Results

This section presents the band structure and the frequency response of the metamaterial described in section 2. In theory, the 2D lattice works as a passband or stopband filter, where for the infinite case without damping, perfect filtering properties occur. Naturally, the generated bandgaps are more dominant in the direction of interest, where the DDA is fully activated. Hence, the following analysis concerns only the direction of amplification, assuming for simplicity one row of unit-cells. An indicative case study is presented based on Dertimanis et al. [24] work on mass-in-mass metamaterials designed to mitigate seismic waves and protect civil engineering structures. According to their publication, three (3) different bands are studied; the first one is between 0.5 – 1.5 Hz, the second one between 1.0 - 2.5 Hz, and the third one between 2.0-5.0 Hz. By assuming that the external mass is $m_L = 1 \text{ Mgr}$, the required resonating mass (m_R) and stiffness (k_R) of the resonator can be estimated from Eq. (10)-(11). Table 1 summarizes the derived values.

Table 1 Unit-cell's structural parameters for the three bandgap scenarios of the study.

Scenario	Band thresholds			Parameters	
	f_L [Hz]	f_H [Hz]	m_L [Mgr]	m_R [Mgr]	k_R [kN/m]
1	0.5	1.5	1.0	8.0	78.96
2	1.0	2.5	1.0	5.25	207.26
3	2	5	1.0	99.0	829.05

3.1. Effect of amplification in bandgap formation and Frequency response

Aiming to study the effect of the DDA amplification mechanism on the band structure and frequency response, the present investigation focuses on scenario 2 (Table 1) and $k_L/k_R = 1$. Herein, the band structure and the frequency response (FRF) of the undamped lattice are calculated. The baseline configuration (simple LRM) is subsequently compared with the model that incorporates the DDA. The dispersion curves in Fig. 5 indicate that the inclusion of the amplification mechanism increases the width of the bandgap, which derives from a drop of the acoustic branch. On the other hand, the optical branch remains unchanged. The frequency response displays that in the very low-frequency region, below 1.0 Hz, the whole curve of the LRM with the DDA is shifted downwards compared to the LRM without the DDA. As expected, the attenuation characteristics are improved as the angle φ of the DDA

increases. The resonances of the structural modes before the bandgap for the case of the LRM without the DDA, are replaced with a subband in the very low-frequency region.

The main drawback of the DDA beneficial effect is the reduction of the depth of the bandgap without however, a significant compromise of the overall performance of the metamaterial. The DDA is a mechanism that amplifies the effective oscillating mass of the LRM. This inertia increase of the unit-cell's resonating mass leads to increase of the bandgap width followed, however, by a reduced decay of the frequency response function within the generated bandgap. Similar reduction of the frequency response decay is observed to conventional LRMs as the resonating mass proportionally increases.

Fig. 5. (left) Dispersion curves and (right) frequency response of the undamped finite lattice for $m_L = 1 \text{ Mgr}$, $m_R = 5.25 \text{ Mgr}$, $k_L/k_R = 1$ and $N = 4$ unit-cells.

3.2. Effect of the Number of Unit-Cells

As a following step, the effect of the number of unit-cells on the overall performance of the periodic metamaterial is investigated. Fig. 6 illustrates the effect of the number of cells on the associated FRFs, for the considered undamped case. It is clear that the attenuation of the signal within the bandgap frequency range decreases as the number of employed unit-cells is reducing. In this analysis, for the sake of comparison, we retain the total mass and stiffness of the studied undamped lattices stable while increasing the number of unit-cells. Increasing the number of unit-cells, increases the depth of the bandgap while bearing a marginal effect on the high-frequency behavior of the system. For $N = 4$, the maximum bandgap depth reaches -40dB , yet for more than $N=10$ units, the metamaterial surpasses -100dB bandgap depth. This increase in bandgap depth is also observed in the very low-frequency subband.

Fig. 6. Frequency response (FRF) of the undamped finite lattice for the first band and $k_L/k_R = 1$, and amplifier angle $\varphi = 75^\circ$ for different number of unit-cells.

3.3. Parametric analysis

A parametric analysis is conducted for three different stiffness ratios k_L/k_R (external to internal spring stiffness), based on the scenarios summarized in Table 1. Fig. 7 presents the dispersion curves for the studied bandgaps and stiffness ratios for the case without DDA and for two amplifier angles, namely 60° and 75° . It is shown that the external stiffness k_L does not significantly influence the frequency band, but affects the behavior of the dispersion curves, mainly the optical branch. For instance, Fig. 7a depicts the dispersion curves for case 1. It is observed that for a specific DDA angle the frequency gap remains essentially unaltered, while at the same time, the optical branch reaches higher frequencies as the stiffness ratio increases due to the significant change of the optical mode. This performance is better reflected in the behavior of the finite lattices.

Fig. 7. Dispersion curves for data of Table 1 and for three stiffness ratios. The simple LRM is compared with the LRM-DDA with $\varphi = 60^\circ$ and 75° (a) first band; (b) second band; (c) third band.

In order to examine in more detail the effect of the amplifier angle compared to the bandgap characteristics of the studied cases, the normalized bandwidth for all the cases and angles is plotted in Fig. 8. This is defined as:

$$b_w = (f_H - f_L)/f_{av}, \quad f_{av} = (f_H + f_L)/2 \quad (20)$$

where f_L and f_H correspond to the lower and upper bandgap limits, respectively, and f_{av} is the mid-gap frequency.

It is illustrated that for large amplifier angles (φ), all cases show a similar normalized bandwidth (b_w) size; however, there are differences in the performance of the metamaterial in the case of smaller angles. For example, the analysis with the parameters of scenario 1 (black line) and $k_L/k_R = 1$ (continuous line) displays the most significant normalized bandwidths when small amplifier angles (φ) are considered; when compared with the case where a larger stiffness ratio is utilized ($k_L/k_R = 100$ or 1000), the arrangement with $k_L/k_R = 1$ indicates a better performance. In addition, when a stiffness ratio $k_L/k_R > 100$ is applied, there is no change in the gap size (b_w); in this case, the normalized bandwidth is only a function of the amplifier's angle. In this study, the amplifiers' angle has been indicatively selected as $\varphi = 60^\circ$ and 75° , respectively. The selection of these relatively large angles has been made to showcase the extraordinary capabilities of the mechanism.

Fig. 8. Normalized bandgap width as a function of the amplifier's angle.

Fig. 9 illustrates the frequency response functions (FRF) that correspond to the dispersion curves of Fig. 7. The specific FRFs refer to a structure with four (4) unit-cells, while again three (3) different cases are compared: without DDA, with DDA of $\varphi = 60^\circ$ and with DDA of $\varphi = 75^\circ$. For every case three (3) stiffness ratios (k_L/k_R) are studied. It is clearly observed that the lower the stiffness ratio is, the more profound the bandgap formation is, and the beneficial effects of the DDA are highlighted. On the contrary, for the stiffness ratio case of $k_L/k_R > 100$, the bandgaps hardly appear and the DDA cannot significantly improve the performance of the lattice, as the natural frequencies of the structure are shifted higher. These results indicate that the normalized bandgap width as a metric, although it may provide a valuable indication of the metamaterial effectiveness, may be deceptive and should be used in conjunction with the frequency response of the structure. In conclusion, the performance of such unit-cells is heavily affected by the stiffness ratio between the inner and the outer springs of the periodic structure and high values should be avoided in the design.

Fig. 9. FRF of the far-right external mass of the finite lattice for $N=4$ unit-cells and for three stiffness ratios (a) 1st band (b) 2nd band (c) 3rd band

4. Conceptual Design of a DDA Metabarrier

Based on the analysis presented in section 3, a fundamental conceptual design for earthquake mitigation in the form of earthquake-proof seismic metabarriers [16,17,45–47] is proposed. These barriers should be compact, lightweight, and their installation and manufacturing should be feasible in order to comprise a realistic solution. The external and internal masses m_L and m_R respectively, should be rigid enough to behave similarly to the theoretical mass-in-mass model, and the selected number of unit-cells should be large enough to reveal the properties of the periodic structure.

Fig. 10 displays a potential arrangement of the proposed system. The locally resonant unit-cells are embedded into the ground in a radial layout, such that the barriers enclose the structures of interest. In the case seismic excitation occurs, the barrier filters out the low-frequency content of the wave by absorbing the seismic energy internally and hence, mitigating the excitation. It is essential to note that due to its geometry, the proposed metabarrier alignment is suitable to protect structures against surface waves [48], which are known for their detrimental effect on man-made structures due to their high amplitude low-frequency components [49]. Mitigation of seismic body waves (S and P waves) is not part of the present study and design concept.

Fig. 10. Schematic representation of (a) the DDA metabarrier radial layout in plan-view and (b) the typical cross-section of the installation.

Under this perspective, the device under investigation is presented in Fig. 11. A reinforced concrete hollow cylindrical section comprises the external mass (m_L) of the unit-cell configuration and a steel cylindrical section the mass of the resonating feature (m_R). The model springs can be realized by some type of elastomeric - rubber material of stiffness equivalent to the theoretical model, which can be reinforced appropriately depending on stiffness and strength requirements. The DDA mechanism can be realized by a simple rigid beam (potentially a robust steel beam) attached to a rigid foundation. The depicted conceptual design comprises only one row of 4 unit-cells and is equivalent to the one-dimensional chain of the locally resonant units. Nonetheless, the design can be further elaborated by adding more rows and unit-cells to improve the device's performance.

Fig. 11. Schematic representation of the proposed metabarrier structure with Dynamic Directional Amplifier (DDA) for mitigation of seismic excitation.

4.1. Dimensioning

Aiming to quantify the material parameters of the unit-cell, a simple iterative process is followed. Initially, the limits of the frequency bandgap, namely f_L and f_H , are selected, together with the magnitude of the external mass (m_L). As a following step, Eq. (10) and

(11) are employed to estimate the required design parameters. Based on the material properties of lightweight concrete and steel, an initial geometry (length and radius for each cylindrical section) is specified, such that the required unit-cell masses are attained.

For the case of the internal and external spring properties (k_L and k_R) of the mass-in-mass structure, common rubber materials like chloroprene rubbers with carbon additives may be adopted, as they demonstrate the desired stiffness properties. The stiffness calculation of the material should consider the required (and also allowable due to the geometry limits of the structure) dimensions of the rubber in order to achieve the desired stiffness of the k_L and k_R elements.

The compressive stiffness of the rubber pad is calculated as follows:

$$k_{comp} = \frac{E_{rubber}A}{h} \quad (21)$$

where E_{rubber} is the elastic Young's Modulus of the rubber material, A is the area of the rubber and h its height.

Obviously, the calculation requires the knowledge of the elastic vertical stiffness modulus E_{rubber} , provided by relevant stress-strain tests of the material in question. For the purpose of this indicative design, the hyper-elastic properties of rubber are neglected; consequently, the calculated value from Eq. (21) is an approximation that can be used as a starting point of the detailed dimensioning of the rubber pads. We remark that the elastic connections can also be realized with conventional metal springs, leaf springs, truss-like springs, or compliant structures that provide the required stiffness.

Based on the rubber properties and the initially selected dimensions of the unit-cell, the outer and inner diameters of the pad are selected such that the elastomer fits to the unit. In case that the required stiffness and/or masses cannot be achieved, the dimensions of the external and resonating features are readjusted. This procedure is repeated until all the parameters correspond to the desired ones. By all means, a more optimized approach can be programmed that can minimize the required materials and maximize the performance of the metastructure; however, this optimization falls out of the scope of the current contribution.

Table 2 displays a feasible set of design data, aiming to obtain the second bandgap, as described in section 3 of this study. The selected properties are based on the analogies presented in Table 1 that correspond to the analysis of the simple LRM configuration without the addition of the DDA mechanism. Therefore, by adopting the above properties, the DDA enhanced lattice should achieve the demanded bandgap and extend its filtering properties to lower frequencies.

Table 2 Indicative unit-cell design parameters of the metabarrier.

Theoretical parameters				
<i>Parameters</i>	<i>value</i>	<i>units</i>	<i>Description</i>	
f_L	1	Hz	Low bandgap frequency limit	
f_H	2.5	Hz	Upper bandgap frequency limit	
m_L	250	kg	External mass of each unit-cell	
m_R	1310	kg	Resonating mass of each unit-cell	
k_R	51.82	kN/m	Stiffness of the internal spring	
k_L	51.82	kN/m	Stiffness of the external spring	
Design parameters				
<i>Parameters</i>	<i>value</i>	<i>units</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>part</i>
ρ_{conc}	1400	kg/m ³	Lightweight concrete density	
D_1	1	m	External diameter of the concrete cylinder	
D_2	0.90	m	Internal diameter of the concrete cylinder	Reinforced concrete – external mass
L_{conc}	1.15	m	Length of concrete cylinder	
m_{conc}	241	kg	Mass of concrete part	
ρ_{steel}	7850	kg/m ³	Steel density	
D_3	0.5	m	Diameter of the steel cylinder	Steel – resonating mass
L_{steel}	0.85	m	Length of steel cylinder	
m_{steel}	1310	kg	Mass of steel part	
E_{rubber}	1800	kPa	Rubber Young's modulus	
t_{rubber}	0.25	m	Height of internal element's rubber	Rubber – internal and external springs
A_{rubber}	$7.85 \cdot 10^{-3}$	m ²	Area of internal element's rubber	
k_{rubber}	56.55	kN/m	Stiffness of rubber element	
φ	75	°	Amplifier angle	DDA

4.2. FE Numerical Investigation of the DDA Metabarrier

Aiming to validate the performance of the designed metabarrier, the finite element code ABAQUS® is employed for a series of frequency response and seismic time-history analyses. The parameters of the model were formulated by adopting the material values of the conceptual design, as indicated in Table 2 of section 4.1. For the purposes of this study, a model with N=4 unit-cells is adopted, and its filtering properties are subsequently investigated. The design follows the second scenario bandgap where $f_L=1$ and $f_H=2.5$ Hz, respectively.

Three-dimensional FE modeling is used to realistically capture the exact geometry of the design, its kinematic boundaries, as well as the appropriate stiffness properties of the proposed materials of the barrier. Linear elastic spring elements and dashpots model the vertical stiffness (K_{rubber}) and damping (C_{rubber}) of the rubber elements attached between the masses (internal and external) of the periodic structure. All parts are discretized by 20-node linear-elastic, quadratic solid brick elements, and tie constraints are assigned between the rubber-concrete and the rubber-steel interface.

A frequency response analysis is subsequently undertaken to derive the transmission curve of this finite length metabarrier; analysis is conducted as a frequency sweep by applying a harmonic excitation at a series of different frequencies and recording the response. The excitation is applied on the first unit-cell and the response of the outer mass of the last unit (end of the lattice) is measured. Fig. 12 depicts the FRF results for the case of a metabarrier with and without the DDA amplifier. As expected from the analytical derivation described in section 3 of this study, results indicate the superiority of the system with the DDA within the frequency domain, especially within the low-frequency region. It is essential to note that the bandgap, due to the addition of the DDA, is extended below the design expectations of the scenario 2 bandgap (without the DDA) and appears to be promising in the mitigation of lower excitation frequencies, well below 1 Hz.

Fig. 12. Frequency response (FRF) of the metabarrier with and without the DDA amplifier, as calculated from the FE numerical analyses.

As a following step, the performance of the DDA metabarrier concept under earthquake excitation is investigated. Various seismic motions corresponding to different hazard levels and frequencies are employed, and time-history analyses are performed to study the potential seismic mitigation properties of this DDA enhanced metabarrier. An artificial accelerogram with an acceleration response spectrum compatible with the Eurocode 8 design response spectrum is generated using the SeismoArtif Software [50] and adopted as a baseline for the time-history analyses. For the purposes of this study, the Artificial Accelerogram is designed in accordance with EC8, incorporating the following seismic properties:

ground type C, spectral peak ground acceleration 0.36 g, spectrum type I and importance class II. In addition, the response of the design is investigated to real earthquake input, for the cases of Aegion (1995) and Lixouri (2014) earthquakes. The seismic motions are simplistically applied as horizontal excitation directly on the first unit-cell and the acceleration of the last unit-cell is calculated as an output.

Fig. 13 presents the response of the DDA enhanced finite lattice, with a relatively low damping ratio equal to $\zeta=3\%$, subjected to the aforementioned artificial and real seismic motions. The spectral content and amplitude of the selected excitations are rich, containing frequencies that are outside the bandgaps generated by the designed DDA metabarrier, presented in Fig. 12. Frequency response (FRF) of the metabarrier with and without the DDA amplifier, as calculated from the FE numerical analyses. This consequently leads to a diverse filtering behavior of the metabarrier, depending on the frequency components of each accelerogram. Fig. 12 (a) – (c) present the filtered acceleration time-histories (measured at the end of the lattice) along with the original applied accelerograms. Results indicate a significant reduction of accelerations within the bandgap regime and a corresponding decrease of the maximum acceleration values. Aiming to better visualize the filtering behavior of the metabarrier, the elastic response spectra that emerge from both the original and filtered acceleration time-histories were calculated and presented in Fig. 13 (d) – (f). As expected from the FRF (Fig. 12), frequencies that coincide with the resonance of the lattice are amplified. However, results show substantial attenuation of the excitation frequencies below 2.5 Hz, indicating the beneficial role of the barrier for the protection of relatively high period structures.

Fig. 13. Response of the DDA metabarrier to seismic excitation: (a) EC8 compatible artificial excitation, (b) Aegion, 1995 earthquake, (c) Lixouri, 2014 earthquake and (d) – (f) corresponding acceleration frequency response spectra for both the original and filtered motions.

In order to assess the feasibility of the proposed metabarrier dimensions, an assessment of the maximum deformations of the internal resonating masses has been undertaken. The displacements (u , v) of the resonating masses as well as the corresponding rotation (θ) of the DDA mechanism were measured. The analyses results indicated that for all selected seismic excitations these deformations are relatively small. Specifically, the maximum displacement (u , v) is less than 2.5cm, while the maximum DDA rotation theta is less than 1 degree. It is clear that these deformation values can be easily accommodated by the proposed conceptual metabarrier design (Table 2).

5. Conclusions

The present study demonstrated the theoretical framework of a novel locally resonant metamaterial consisting of dynamically amplified resonating masses. The novelty lies in the simplicity of the proposed system. The dynamic directional amplification (DDA) mechanism is realized without additional masses or complex geometries since the amplification can be achieved by coupling the kinematic DoFs of the resonating mass by incorporating a rigid link in the metamaterial lattice.

It is demonstrated that using dynamic amplification and a moderate number of unit-cells, relatively deep bandgaps at low frequencies can be obtained. By exploiting the dynamic mass of the proposed mass-in-mass periodic structure, it is illustrated that better dispersion properties are obtained compared to the conventional locally resonant metamaterials of equivalent structure. Thus, significant filtering characteristics are achieved while reducing

the large parasitic resonating masses. The main drawback of the DDA beneficial effects is the reduction of the maximum depth of the bandgap, without however, a significant compromise of the overall performance of the metamaterial. Another potential disadvantage of the mechanism is the diversion of the resonating mass movement perpendicular to the direction of the external applied action; this leads to mass movement in both axes (2D movement in the horizontal and vertical axis) that needs to be accommodated depending on the application and design of the lattice structure.

An indicative implementation of the DDA enhanced concept as a seismic protection mechanism in the form of a metabarrier is subsequently proposed. A conceptual design paradigm is numerically analyzed by employing time-history analyses and comprises a priori proof of concept of a simple, feasible design that can be exploited as a baseline for future, more detailed prototypes. Results indicated the beneficial role of the device and DDA mechanism, hence placing the concept as a potential alternative to existing seismic isolation concepts and structural protection devices. In the future, the design may be converted appropriately to achieve wider bandgaps and further broaden the mitigation properties of the DDA metabarrier within the frequency domain.

Based on all the above observations, the proposed framework may be incorporated in further applications such as mechanical filters, sound and vibration isolators, or acoustic panels, as it provided promising outcomes and information towards the development of acoustic metamaterial designs, able to offer low-frequency isolation and vibration control.

Acknowledgments

Moris Kalderon and Antonios Mantakas would like to acknowledge the financial support provided by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant (Grant Agreement No. INSPIRE-813424, "INSPIRE—Innovative Ground Interface Concepts for Structure Protection").

Declarations of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Appendix

Following is the derivation of Eq. (2). In Fig. 1, connecting the amplification mass to the origin of the local CSYS via a hinged, rigid, massless rod imposes a kinematic constraint between the degrees of freedom u and v . The lumped parameter model is described by the coordinates of the amplification mass (m) at a generic position $A(x, y) = (x_0 + u, y_0 - v)$, where x_0, y_0 are the initial coordinates of the mass. The initial angle between the horizontal axis and the link $\varphi^o = \text{atan}\left(\frac{x_0}{y_0}\right)$ and the rotation of the rod θ^o at the generic position A of the moving mass. Then the kinetic (T) and potential (V) energies of the system are calculated as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2}m(\dot{u}^2 + \dot{v}^2) = \frac{1}{2}m\left(1 + \frac{x^2}{y^2}\right)\dot{u}^2 = \frac{1}{2}mL^2\frac{\dot{u}^2}{y^2} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$V = \frac{1}{2}k_x(l_x - l_{xi})^2 + \frac{1}{2}k_y(l_y - l_{yi})^2 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where l_{xi}, l_{yi} and l_x, l_y are the deformations of the springs at the initial and a generic position, respectively.

For $L = T - U$ and by application of the Lagrange principle:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{u}}\right) - \frac{\partial T}{\partial u} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} = 0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

the equation of motion is obtained after linearization as:

$$\frac{mL^2}{y_0^2}\ddot{u} + \left[k_x + k_y\left(\frac{x_0}{y_0}\right)^2\right]u = F \quad (\text{A.4})$$

assuming small displacements of the mass m as the springs' deformations are nonlinear functions of u, v .

This can be rewritten as:

$$m[1 + \tan^2(\varphi)]\ddot{u} + [k_x + k_y \tan^2(\varphi)]u = F \quad (\text{A.5})$$

or for $\rho = \tan\varphi$

$$m[1 + \rho^2]\ddot{u} + [k_x + k_y\rho^2]u = F \quad (\text{A.6})$$

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